

A CLINICAL CASE STUDY ON KARNABADHIRYA WITH AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT

Dr. Deepti Sharma*

Assistant Professor, Shalaky Tantra Department, L.N. Ayurved college and Hospital, LNCT University, Bhopal (M.P).

Article Received on 15 May 2026,
Article Revised on 05 June 2026,
Article Published on 16 June 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20678561>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Deepti Sharma

Assistant Professor, Shalaky Tantra
Department, L.N. Ayurved college
and Hospital, LNCT University,
Bhopal (M.P).

How to cite this Article: Dr. Deepti Sharma* (2026). A Clinical Case Study on Karnabadhira With Ayurvedic Management. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(12), 724-730. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Ageing is the process during which structural and functional changes accumulate in an organism as a result of the passage of time. The changes manifest as a decline from the organism's peak physiological functions. Ageing is biological clock of all human body. Presbycusis is a hidden disability, one among the many socio-medical problems. The hearing impairment in elderly people is described as presbycusis. Hearing problem among elderly people is a major issue and a person with hearing loss may be unable to hear doorbells and alarms, to respond while talking with anyone, etc. All this can make them feel frustrated, lonely, and depressed. It is the third most common chronic condition after arthritis and hypertensive diseases among elders. Hearing loss can be improved by using the hearing aids. Hearing aids work well for some while for others; it may not be a perfect solution due to many reasons

such as some people do not buy aids that meet their needs, incorrect amplification adjustments, low custom design, etc. In classics of Ayurveda this ailment has been described as *karnabaadhira* under the heading of ear diseases. *Karnapurana* (Instillation of medicated oil into the external auditory canal) is one of the major treatments for ear diseases explained in classics. A case report of 65-year-old male who presented with complaints of reduced hearing and tinnitus in both ears has been presented here.

KEYWORDS: *Bilwataila*, *karnabaadhira*, *karnapurana*, presbycusis.

INTRODUCTION

Hearing impairment is the most frequent sensory deficit in human populations, affecting more than 278 million people in the world. In India, 63 million people (6.3%) suffer from significant auditory loss.^[1] The prevalence of presbycusis rises with age, ranging from 25% to 40% of the population aged 65 years, 40-66% in patients older than 75 years, and more than 80% in patients older than 85 years.^[2] Risk factors for presbycusis include systemic diseases and poor habits that cause inner ear damage and lead to impaired hearing. Age, the male gender, diabetes mellitus, hypertension and hereditary hearing loss are all identified as risk factors. Poorly controlled hypertension or diabetes may pre-dispose to hearing impairment through the occurrence of chronic arteriosclerosis which in turn causes a reduction in the blood supply to the inner ear, as these are common chronic diseases among older adults. Hearing loss due to aging occurs from a combination of environmental and genetic factors. However, unfortunately, for various reasons the deafness has not drawn enough attention.

In the majority of presbycusis cases, hearing loss develops as a consequence of degeneration of the inner ear, to be more precise the area of the inner ear containing microscopic blood vessels.

There are additional changes to hair cells accompanied by loss of these cells and further hearing problems.^[3] Treatment for presbycusis in the majority of cases includes appropriate hearing aids. This is only a partial solution of the problem. However, it has its own limitations and drawbacks. Untreated presbycusis leads to social isolation, and depression, and may cause or worsen cognitive impairment and dementia.^[4] In Ayurveda it can be taken as *vaardhakyajanya baadharya* (senile deafness) one of the *karnagata roga* (ear disease) which is having the main symptom as reduced hearing.^[5]

Most hearing loss is either due to the disturbance of *vata dosha* alone or vitiation of *vata-kapha* together. Here *kaphavardhak ahar* and *vardhakya* (senility) are the main etiological factors, which result in the vitiation of *vata* and *kapha dosha*. *Vata* vitiation can result in damage to the auditory nerve and nerve endings, which can lead to hearing loss and ringing in the ear.

When *kapha* is vitiated, there is obstruction of the sound pathway. Finally, disturbances of *vata* as well as *kapha* can affect the auditory nerve resulting in degeneration of the end organs of hearing or obstructions to the flow of nerve impulses, ending in presbycusis.

The main treatment of *karnagata rogas* is *Karnapurana*. As the root cause for *karnagata rogas* lies in the *shabdavaha srotas* and the *dosha* involved is *vata dosha*, hence the treatment of choice is *karnapurana*. *Yogratnakar* states that “*Puranam katutailam hitam vataghnameva cha*”^[6] hence *Karnapurana* was selected as treatment of choice to combat the root cause of *baadhiryā* (deafness). This case showed good results.

CASE REPORT

A 65-year-old male presented with the complaints of reduced hearing in both ears associated with occasional occurrence of tinnitus, since 1 year.

On examination

On local examination of the ear [Table 1] the pinna, external auditory canal and tympanic membrane were normal. On tuning fork test, air conduction and bone conduction were reduced, which interprets the low +^{ve} Rinne. On pure tone audiometric examination, the case was diagnosed as moderately severe sensori-neural hearing loss. The patient was able to hear and understand on shouting loudly.

Table 1: Local examination of ear.

EXTERNAL EAR	RIGHT SIDE	LEFT SIDE
SIZE	NORMAL	NORMAL
SHAPE	NORMAL	NORMAL
PREAURICULAR AREA	NORMAL	NORMAL
POSTAURICULAR AREA	NORMAL	NORMAL
EXTERNAL ACOUSTIC MEATUS	NAD	NAD
TYMPANIC MEMBRANE	INTACT	INTACT

Past History

Patient had taken hearing aid 1 year back but it was of no use.

Procedures administered to the patient

The patient was administered with *Karnapurana* once daily for 7 consecutive days [Figure 1]. The treatment was repeated after 7 days. The details of the procedures are described in Table 2.

Figure: 1.

Poorvakarma	Abhyanga with tila tail (local massage) Swedan (sudation therapy)
Pradhankarma	Instilled 6 drops of bilwadi tail in both ear for 5 min.
Paschat karma	Stuff the ear with cotton to avoid direct exposure toward heat, cold, dust and wind

Pathya(Do's)-Advised to take *laghu(light)* ,*supachya(easy to digest)* and *ushna(warm)* *ahaara*, *ghritapana* (intake of ghee), wheat, rice, green gram, brinjal, drum stick, bitter gourd, *bhrahmacharya* (maintaining celibacy), *alpa bhashana*, etc., which pacifies The *vata dosha*.

Apathya (Dont's)- Advised not to take head bath, drink cold water or other drinks, clean ears, exposure to cold wind, exercise, brushing the teeth with sticks,etc. which leads to aggravation of *vata dosha*.

RESULTS

The tinnitus was reduced and subjective improvement in hearing was observed by 1 months. The patient was able to hear sounds and understand words spoken loudly. The patient was advised to avoid exposure to loud noise. With a follow-up for a period of 1 month, the patient had a mild improvement in hearing. Meanwhile, he was prescribed oral medication of, *Indu vati* one tablet twice daily, *Ashwagandhadi churna* 1tsp BD with milk and *Karnapurana* with *bilwadi taila*.

DISCUSSION

Loss of hearing is one of the important causes of psychological trauma of the sensory losses and this is exactly how the deaf drowns in a sea of silence.^[7] The degenerative changes that occur in the cells of organ of corti and nerve fibers result in a slow, progressive deafness which may be associated with tinnitus.^[8]

Mode of action

Karnaabhyanga (Massage of the ear)

Here for *karnaabhyanga murchita tilataila* (processed sesame seed oil) was used. *Taila* is having *vyavayi, vikaasi, sukshma, vishada, guru and sara* properties, *ushna veerya* and *madhura vipaka*. Hence mainly acts on vitiated *vata dosha* and pacifies it and normalizes its function.

As *Tila taila* is having *brihana(nourishing)*^[9] the nourishment of *shravanendriya(ear)* and to improve the hearing mechanism.

Bhashpaswedana(Sudation therapy)

Swedana karma by virtue of its properties like *ushna, sara, snigdha, sukshma, and shtira*, etc., aids quicker absorption of oil into the ear and helps in *vata shaman* (pacification of *vata dosha*), improves the blood circulation and gives strength to the ears.^[10] These actions in turn help to improve auditory function.

Karnapurana (Instillation of medicated oil into external auditory canal)

The ears are said to be the seat of *vata dosha* and are responsible for hearing mechanism as Quoted in Asthanga Hridaya “*Pakwashayakatisakthishrotasthi.....*”^[11] “*Buddhihridayendriya chitta drik.*”^[11] The disease *baadhira* occurs in ears is mainly due to vitiation of *vata dosha*. *Karnapurana* does the *vata shamana* and maintains the normal hearing capacity, as quoted told by *Acharya Charaka* “*na karnarogaa vatottaha nochchai shrutihi na badiryam syannityam karma tarpanaat*”^[12] *Bilwa taila* was used for *karnapurana*. *Bilwa* exhibits *ushna veerya* and *vatahara and kaphahara*. action and helps restore *vata dosha* to normal. In one of the research works on leaf extract of *Bilwa* the results have shown the regeneration of damaged cells in pancreas.^[13] *Bhavaprakash Nighantu* mentions that *Bilwa* exhibits action on nerves and hence is considered as a *nadi balya* (gives strength to nerves) drug.^[14] Thus, it may be inferred that *Bilwa* may be helping in nourishment of the ear cells as well as regeneration of damaged cells in deafness.

Oral medication

Ashwagandhadi churna contains *Ashwagandha*, *Yastimadhu*, *Haridra*, and *Rasna*, which are used to heal and regenerate damaged nerve cells, thus improving the nerve function. *Indu vati* mainly contains *Suvarna bhasma* and *Abhraka bhasma* which are considered as immune modulatory medicines, used to reduce the deleterious effects of stress and to boost the immune status of the body. These compounds exert a *rasayana* effect. As the patient was elderly, we gave *rasayana* drugs to improve *rasa* and *rakta dhatus*. This might have contributed in the early improvement in sensori-neural hearing loss and prevented further deterioration of this condition. A correction of abnormalities in the body tissues indirectly helps in improvement in hearing by reducing the dysfunction of the inner ear.

This study shows that there is significant improvement in hearing mechanism and there were no adverse effects seen throughout the treatment. The mode of treatment was found to be effective, safe and easy to implement. Thus, this paper aims at presenting a treatment protocol mentioned in the Ayurvedic texts that is effective in treating the known cause of the condition and improving the functional integrity of ear.

REFERENCES

1. GargS, ChadhaS, MalhotraS, AgarwalAK. Deafness:Burden, preventionandcontrolin India. *Natl. Med. J. , India*. 2009; 22: 79–81. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. YuehB, ShapiroN, MacLeanCH, ShekellePG. Screeningandmanagementofadult hearing loss inprimarycare:Scientificreview. *JAMA*, 2003; 289: 1976-85. [PubMed] [GoogleScholar]
3. Agerelatedhearingloss, 2012. [Lastupdatedon10thJuly]. Available from<http://www.deafnessresearch.org.uk/content/your-hearing/main-types-of-hearing-loss/age-related-hearing-loss>.
4. Dalton DS, Cruickshanks KJ, Klein BE, Klein R, Wiley TL, NondahlDM. The impact of hearing loss on quality of life in older adults. *Gerontologist*. 2003; 43: 661–8. [PubMed][GoogleScholar]
5. DwivediR. Reprinted. Ch. 12. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy. Shalaky Tantra (Nimi Tantra) Karna-Badiryaya Adhyaya, 2006; 397. [Google Scholar]
6. ShastriSB, editor. 8thed. Verse14. Varanasi:ChaukhambaSanskrit Sansthan; Shastri SL, Commentator. Vidyotini Hindi Teeka on Yogaratnakara, Karnaroga Chikitsa; 2004: 314. [GoogleScholar]

7. BSTuli, TuliIP, SinghAD, TuliNK. , editors. *Ch14-Deafnessandvariousrehabilitative measures*. 1st ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers; TextbookofEar, Nos0e, and Throat; 2005: 110. [GoogleScholar]
8. MaqboolM. 8thed. NewDelhi:JaypeeBrothers; Text book of Ear, Nose, and Throat Diseases, 1993; 174. [Google Scholar]
9. MurthyS. 2nded. Ch. 45, Verse1 12-113. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surabharati Prakashan; Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Part-I, Sutra Sthana; 2004: 348. [Google Scholar]
10. AcharyaYT. *Part-I, SutraSthana*. Reprinted. Ch. 22, Verse16. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surabharati Prakashan;. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha. Revised by Charaka and Dridhabala with Ayurveda Dipika Hindi Commentary, 2008; 120. [Google Scholar]
11. Gupta A. *Part-I, Vidyotini Hindi Commentary Sutrasthana*. Reprint ed. Ch. 12, verse 1-4. Varanasi:ChaukhambaSanskrit Sansthan;2005. AsthangaHridayaofVagbhata;p. 90. [GoogleScholar].
12. AcharyaYT. *Part-I Sutra Sthana*. Ch. 5, Verse84. V aranasi: ChaukhambaSurabharati Prakashan;. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha, Revised byCharakaandDridhabalawith Ayurveda Dipika Hindi Cmmentary; 2008: 42. [Google Scholar]
13. Das AV, PadayattiPS, PauloseCS. EffectofleafextractofAegle marmelos(L.)Correaex Roxb. on histological and ultra structuralchanges in tissues ofstreptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Indian J. Exp. Biol.* , 1996; 34: 341–5. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
14. ShastryJL. Varanasi:ChaukhambaOrientalia;. IllustratedDravyagunaVijnana; 2005; 2: 111. [GoogleScholar]